

Interactive AR Textbook

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Abstract: The impact of technological advancement on the education system, particularly the need for innovation in its use in teaching and learning, is significant. However, the disclosure of a previous study found that a total of 269,332 primary school students across the country were not able to master the basic 3M skills of reading, counting, and writing. Therefore, this study aims to develop an Interactive AR textbook to learn the vowels a, e, è, i, o, and u. Evaluation of the effectiveness of using Interactive AR Textbooks, especially from the design point of view and to user experience and cognitive style in the context of grade 1 (7 years) primary school in the State of Perak. This innovation uses metaverse, an augmented reality technology, combined with the physical material of the Grade 1 Bahasa Melayu Textbook (KSSR). This study uses design-based research (DBR) as design research, which is divided into four phases: Phase I (analysis), Phase II (development), Phase III (evaluation), and Phase IV (documentation). Six experts were selected to verify the application. It was tested for usability and student performance on 314 grade 1 (7 years) primary school students in the State of Perak. The results revealed that the Interactive AR Textbook can be used to learn vowels a, e, è, i, o, and u based on expert agreement in terms of usability (99%), ease of use (98%), ease of learning (96%), and motivation (100%). Results show that Interactive AR Textbooks can increase motivation for learning Malay vowels, making them beneficial for grade 1 students, teachers, and schools. This application enables the creation of a realistic, authentic, engaging, and entertaining learning environment. This study also acknowledges the limitations and future recommendations of this study.

Keywords: Interactive Textbooks; Augmented Reality; Digital Education; 3M skills; Metaverse.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Innovative, forward-thinking, and competitive materials are required for Revolution 4.0 education. Considering Polyzou et al. (2021) the current state of education, digitization of instruction is a primary concern. A previous study, however, revealed that 269,332 primary school students nationwide lacked proficiency in the three fundamental 3M skills reading, counting, and writing. The issues of high attrition rates and deficiencies in the 3M mastery skills pertaining to digital education, as emphasised by the Ministry of Education (MOE) in 2023, constitute an urgent matter within the realm of education. Numerous studies, like those conducted by Zakari et al. (2022) and Mazlan et al. (2022), underscore the challenges students face, particularly in the domains of reading, writing, and numeracy. Given the statistical data indicating that a considerable proportion of students' encounter difficulties in these fundamental abilities, it is indisputable that focused interventions and pedagogical reforms are imperative to rectify these deficiencies. Additionally, Hasan et al. (2020) identify specific elements that contribute to student deficiencies, such as the absence of appropriate thinking tools and graphics. This underscores the significance of integrating a variety of instructional approaches and materials in order

to improve students' understanding and proficiency. The necessity for inventive and imaginative educational resources becomes progressively apparent in response to the dynamic educational environment, as underscored by Polyzou et al. (2021).

Figure 1. The need for Orang Asli in Perak primary schools' interactive AR textbook prototype. (Noraini & Ekram, 2024)

The demand for a 4.0 education revolution emphasises the importance of adaptive and competitive strategies to tackle the difficulties associated with acquiring fundamental abilities such as reading, writing, and numeracy in the realm of digital education (Ramli et al. 2023). This observation underscores the potential for utilising technology to improve conventional pedagogical approaches and create interactive and efficacious educational resources that accommodate a wide range of learners' requirements and cultivate comprehensive mastery in students. Thus, educators and policymakers can nurture a more inclusive and robust educational environment that enables every student to excel by recognising these weaknesses and dropout rates in conjunction with a dedication to innovation.

Reading is an activity that contributes to the expansion of one's knowledge. This opinion is supported by this study (Balanadam and KhairulAzhar 2021; Jamaludin 2021). Rashid et al., discovered a deficiency in comprehension and reading mastery abilities among 161 rural primary school students in Negeri Sembilan, Pahang, and Sarawak, who were in grades 4 and 5 in line with the opinion of the study (Abdul Rashid Jamian 2011). Consequently, primary school reading performance continues to endure obstacles. These students fail to comprehend the text's facts and sentence meaning (minimum = 3.24; average = 3.40; standard deviation = 0.71), respectively (sp = 0.60)(Abdul Halim Masnan, Siok Peh, and Azila Alias 2021). Students in Year 1 and a limited number of those in Levels 4 and 5 of primary school continue to grapple with reading fluency, comprehension, and text recognition. The findings of the research revealed (Haimi et al. 2020; Mohd Adnan et al. 2021; Nurul 2010).

Technology has a major impact on education, especially the demand for innovation in teaching and learning. Prior research indicated that 269,332 primary school pupils nationwide could not read, count, or write. This alarming statistic highlights the urgent need for educational reform and the integration of innovative technologies to address the learning gaps among primary school students. Assistance in learning the vowels a, e, è, i, o, and u from the Year Bahasa Melayu Topic 1 syllabus (KSSR) for Year 1 Primary School students.

The research objectives for this study can be referred to as follows:

1. Developing an AR textbook for the vowels a, e, è, i, o, and u.
2. By integrating AR into traditional textbooks, the study aims to leverage the benefits of technology to improve learning outcomes.
3. Reviewing the usefulness of Interactive AR Textbooks in Perak primary school education, including design, user experience (motivation), and cognitive style.

2. METHOD AND MATERIAL

2.1 Research Design

Methodology serves as the foundational component of a research investigation. To acquire its findings, each research study employs a distinct methodology. As outlined in the cited sources (Abdusselam and Kilis 2021; Scott, Wenderoth, and Doherty 2020), the researcher employed the Design-Based Research (DBR) methodology. "Engineering research," "formative evaluation," and "development research" are subsets of "design research" that are further classified under this overarching term. At times, scholars in the learning sciences implement designer-based research (DBR), a methodology that has its roots in the field of education. Responses to issues (also referred to as "interventions") are executed during the initial phase of the DBR procedure (FRÅGÅT 2022).

Figure 2 illustrates, using design-based research (DBR), the researcher gathered data with the participation and education of Orang Asli students through the implementation of augmented reality (AR) experiences. Researchers identified and resolved any challenges that students might encounter when utilising augmented reality experiences by employing DBR (Scott et al. 2020). DBR may be employed by researchers to generate evidence-based recommendations regarding the implementation of augmented reality (AR) interactive textbooks in the classroom. Phase I (analysis), Phase II (development), Phase III (evaluation), and Phase IV (documentation) comprise the design research model utilised in this study, which is design-based research (DBR). A.D.D.I.E. models, Design-Based Research (DBR), and the animation production process can be utilised by educators, researchers, and animators in concert to produce augmented reality (AR) interactive textbooks that are both captivating and efficacious, as evidenced by the study (Abdusselam and Kilis 2021).

Figure 2. Relationship between the animation production process and Design-Based Research (DBR)

2.1.1 Phase I (Analysis): Analysis of the Requirements for an Interactive AR Textbook

The researcher assessed the application's suitability to assist Orang Asli students in recognising the vowels a, e, è, i, o, and u as presented in the KSSR Bahasa Melayu textbook Grade 1. Various procedures were employed during this stage to ascertain and label issues. Following problem identification, an analysis is conducted to ascertain the underlying cause or factors associated with the issue. The analysis procedure comprises multiple components:

- i. User evaluation of the KSSR Malay Textbook for Grade 1.
- ii. Analysis of 3M learning and achievement
- iii. Determine whether a mobile application necessary for acquiring the vowels a, e, è, i, o, and u is required.

During the analysis phase, in light of Figure 4, the researcher thoroughly investigates all facets that must be incorporated during the creation of the Interactive AR Textbook application. Developing software for educational objectives typically entails ongoing collaboration among multiple stakeholders, research, and evaluation of diverse facets. Further consideration should be given to the validity of the content in order to generate an instructional analysis that determines whether the software fulfils the anticipated objectives and competencies. Additionally, interview sessions were conducted to determine whether a mobile application for learning the vowels a, e, è, i, o, and u was necessary.

Figure 3. Bahasa Melayu textbook KSSR, (a) textbook cover (b) page 6 topic *Mendengar dan Bertutur*.

2.1.2 Phase II (Development): Design and Development of an Interactive AR Textbook

In order to develop an interactive augmented reality textbook prototype, one must initially select various forms of content, including text, video, animation, and 3D models, that are in accordance with the prescribed KSSR Grade 1 Bahasa Malay syllabus, which can be found in Table 1. Determine whether the presentation format is interactive, inert, narrated, linear, or non-linear. Keeping the syllabus unchanged, the content was scaled and quality-controlled to permit AR integration and student accessibility. Interactive games and cards boost student engagement and learning. According to the Interactive AR Textbook design strategy, building AR experiences involves planning, prototyping, coding, revising, and testing AR material on certain platforms and tools.

Figure 4. Flowchart of Interactive AR Textbook.

Table 1. The screenshot of Interactive AR Textbook application

Interactive AR Textbook App Interface	Justification
	<p>Figure 5 displays the main screen of the Interactive AR Textbook app. There will be another screen after clicking the "Mula" button.</p>
	<p>Figure 6 shows the vowel selection 'menu' <i>a, e, è, i, o, and u</i>. This interface is located in the second scene. Each text and graphic in this interface have its own layer. The user needs to select and click on the word <i>ayam, ekor, enam, itik, obor</i> or <i>udang</i> to change it. As a result, the user has to press the continue button to go to the next section.</p>

Figure 6. Menu Vowel option

Figure 7. Vowel A section

Figure 7 presents the 'A' vowel selection interface and the chicken display which symbolises the spelling of A to *ayam*. This interface has two-dimension options, which are 2D and 3 dimensions. Each text and graphic in this interface have its own layer in addition to producing the vocal and spelling sounds of *ayam* and crowing chickens. The user has to press on the desired character to change it. The user has to press the continue button to go to the next section.

Figure 8. Vowel E section

Figure 8 shows the topic's subtopic interface or options. This interface is in the 'E' vowel scene. All text and graphics in this interface have layers. This page offers 2D and 3D possibilities. This interface has layers for each text and visual and produces vocal sounds, spelling sounds of '*enam*', and whistling. Each subtopic has buttons. Clicking takes you to the topic scene.

Figure 9. Vowel 'E' section

Figure 9 shows the topic's subtopic interface or options. This interface is in the 'E' vowel scene. All text and graphics in this interface have layers. This page offers 2D and 3D possibilities. This interface's texts and graphics have layers and produce vocal and spelling sounds of '*ekor*' of cat and meowing cat. Each subtopic has buttons. Clicking takes you to the topic scene.

Figure 10. Vowel I section

The subtopic interface or topic options are shown in Figure 10. This interface is in the 'I' vowel scene. All text and graphics in this interface have layers. This page offers 2D and 3D possibilities. This interface produces vocal noises, spelling sounds of '*itik*' and quacking duck, and layers for each text and picture. Each subtopic has buttons. Clicking takes you to the topic scene.

Figure 11. Vowel O section

Figure 11 depicts the topic's subtopic interface or options. This interface is in the 'O' vowel scene. All text and graphics in this interface have layers. This page offers 2D and 3D possibilities. This interface features layers for each text and picture and produces vocal and spelling sounds of '*obor*' and torch burn. Each subtopic has buttons. Clicking takes you to the topic scene.

Figure 12. Vowel U section

Figure 12 shows the topic settings, or subtopic interface. 'U' vowel scene interface. This interface offers layers for text and graphics. There are 2D and 3D options on this page. Besides the vocal sounds and writing sounds of 'udang' and water splash, each text and visual in this interface has its own layer. Subtopics have buttons. Clicking navigates to the topic scene.

Figure 13. Appreciation and encouragement section

Figure 13 - The last section gives appreciation and words of encouragement to users who finish mentioning and complaining about vocal discomfort. Then, the user must press the home button to repeat the activities.

2.1.3 Phase III (Evaluation): Interactive AR Textbook Evaluation

The evaluation of the Interactive AR Textbook constitutes the final phase. The researcher assesses student motivation and efficacy in relation to the application.

2.1.4 Phase IV (Documentation): Evaluate the solution and refine it based on feedback

The phases of design are delineated in the Phase documentation by DBR researchers in order to facilitate logical decision-making regarding the selection and application of methods. In addition, they assess the efficacy of the artefacts via summative and formative assessments employing a combination of qualitative and quantitative methodologies. They refine the artefacts in response to the evaluation results in order to resolve any identified issues and increase their efficacy. In addition to the research questions, design decisions, evaluation methods, and refinement strategies, they conclude by documenting the DBR process. For subsequent research and development endeavours, the documentation is an invaluable resource. Phase documentation of the Interactive AR Textbook Application for 3M Orang Asli Students in primary school may utilise DBR to ensure that the students' learning experiences and emotions are effectively captured.

2.2 Population and Sample

The experiment involved 62 Orang Asli students, all of whom were seven years old, who were enrolled in a primary school. The study sample comprises respondents who have been specifically chosen to serve as representatives of the population. The researchers investigated the degree to which mobile application-based learning and instruction can benefit both instructors and learners. In conducting this investigation, 62 Orang Asli students were guided by research ethics. Parents were provided with consent forms and subsequently granted permission and agreement for their offspring to partake in the aforementioned study.

Figure 14. Perak State Primary School students implement an interactive AR textbook

2.3. Instrument

Three instruments were utilised in this research: performance evaluations, observation checklists, and interview inquiries. The interview comprised seven inquiries pertaining to the necessity of Interactive AR Textbook applications for vowels a, e, è, i, o, and u learning among primary school Orang Asli students. Then, an observation checklist pertaining to the Interactive AR Textbook's usability was formulated. Student performance in vowels a, e, è, i, o, and u learning is subsequently assessed through performance assessments. The pre-test and post-test consist of 22 questions each, both pertaining to the vowels a, e, i, o, u, and are administered to primary school Orang Asli students. Six experts independently validated each instrument, ensuring that it remained valid and reliable for the purposes of this study.

2.4 Data Analysis

The researcher conducted a number of data analyses, including descriptive and thematic analyses, percentages, agreement percentages, pre-test and post-test scores, a normality test, and a paired sample t-test, in order to address the research questions.

3. FINDINGS

This study uses design-based research (DBR) as design research, which is divided into four phases: Phase I (analysis), Phase II (development), Phase III (evaluation), and Phase IV (documentation). Six experts were selected to verify the application. It was tested for usability and student performance on 314 first-year students among grade 1 (7 years) primary school students in the State of Perak. The results revealed that the Interactive AR Textbook can be used to learn vowels a, e, è, i, o, and u based on expert agreement in terms of:

- a. usability (99%),
- b. ease of use (98%),
- c. ease of learning (96%),
- d. and motivation (100%).

Results show that Interactive AR Textbooks can increase motivation for learning Malay vowels, making them beneficial for grade 1 students, teachers, and schools. This application enables the creation of a realistic, authentic, engaging, and entertaining learning environment.

Table 2. Results of the observation on the usability of Interactive AR Textbook

	Teacher 1	Teacher 2	Teacher 3	Teacher 4	Teacher 5	Teacher 6	Total level of agreement	Percent of teachers' agreements (%)
Level of agreements								
USEFULNESS							99	
1. Primary School students like the interface of The Interactive AR Textbook.	3	3	2	3	3	3	9/9	100
2. Primary School students like the colors in The Interactive AR Textbook.	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100
3. The Interactive AR Textbook display is appropriate for Primary School students in learning the vowels <i>a, e, è, i, o,</i> and <i>u</i> .	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100
4. Primary School students can read the text in The Interactive AR Textbook easily	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100
5. Primary School students like the graphic visuals displayed in The Interactive AR Textbook	3	3	3	3	2	3	8/9	88.88
6. Overall, Primary School students are satisfied with Interactive AR Textbook	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100
EASE OF USE								98
7. Primary School students can use The Interactive AR Textbook easily.	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100
8. The link in The Interactive AR Textbook menu works properly for Primary School students.	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100
9. The organization of learning materials in The Interactive AR Textbook is well-structured for Primary School students.	3	3	3	3	3	3	8/9	100

10. Primary School students can easily access all the content in The Interactive AR Textbook	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100
11. The Interactive AR Textbook application has prominent and interactive features with excellent multimedia elements for Primary School	3	3	3	3	2	3	8/9	88.88
EASE OF LEARNING								96
12. Primary School Grade 1 students can easily understand the learning content in The Interactive AR Textbook.	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100
13. The topic of each lesson in The Interactive AR Textbook is relevant to the instructional materials.	3	3	3	3	2	3	8/9	88.88
14. The content in The Interactive AR Textbook is flexible for Primary School Grade 1 students.	3	3	3	3	2	3	8/9	88.88
15. Primary School Grade 1 students can easily find the source of learning materials provided by teachers.	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100
MOTIVATION								100
16. Students enjoy the challenge of learning this learning material.	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100
17. Students enjoy gaining new knowledge.	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100
18. Students learn more than necessary because I like to learn.	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100
19. Students are very happy with my progress which makes me enthusiastic to continue learning.	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100

20. Students look forward to reading more deeply about some subjects because I love them.	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100
21. When a student's lesson goes well, the student looks very happy.	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100
22. Students become physically excited when my learning goes well.	3	3	3	3	3	3	9/9	100

Note: Level of agreement (3: Strongly agree, 2: Agree, 1: Disagree)

Interactive AR Textbook is a learning application for mobile devices that functions as a textbook. The use of mobile applications in the classroom has benefits for Grade 1 primary school students. The Interactive AR Textbook promotes the acquisition of the vowel a, e, è, i, o, and u among primary school students through its interactive design. A robust interface design significantly affects the way in which children interact with touch-screen applications, according to the findings of a number of independently conducted studies. This opinion is supported by this study (R. Wang 2022; X. Wang 2022; Zhao and Wang 2022). Additionally, the mobile application's usability is critical in order to assist students in its operation. The multimedia components and prominent, interactive features of the Interactive AR Textbook make it an ideal resource for primary school Aboriginal students. The study argues by (Lee et al. 2018; Wang et al. 2022). Furthermore, the Interactive AR Textbook exhibits a commendable level of organisation in its compilation of educational resources tailored specifically for Grade 1 Malay Language students in primary school.

Usability of mobile applications also considers ease of learning to be an essential component. An inverse relationship exists between ease of learning and both user satisfaction and adoption rates. Furthermore, user satisfaction with the interactive augmented reality textbook is critical. Al-Basumatary et al. corroborated this notion, asserting that user satisfaction serves as the primary factor influencing both loyalty and the propensity to recommend this particular application to others absorb by (Basumatary and Maity 2023).

Consistent with the findings of Jdaitawi et al., the outcomes of this research demonstrate that learning and hand-eye coordination are enhanced when fine psychomotor skills are integrated with conceptual understanding (Jdaitawi et al. 2023). Moreover, the results of this research align with those of AlNajdi et al., and Chang et al., which indicate that the adoption of technological tools in education has increased due to the gradual transition from traditional textbooks and instructional videos to digital-based media, including educational games, electronic textbooks, and instructional videos. This study provides support for this view (AlNajdi 2022; Chang et al. 2020). As a result, it can be deduced that the Interactive AR Textbook application is beneficial in all respects and has the potential to assist Grade 1 in primary schools in enhancing their 3M mastery of vocal learning.

3.1 Student Performance

In 314 of primary school grade 1 Malay-learning students, the pre- and post-tests were given. An examination of 62 Grade 1 kids at a school in the State of Perak, both before and after the test, is shown in Figure 15. Positive progress is shown in the pre- and post-test findings. In the post-test, every one of the 62 students demonstrated improvement over the pre-test response. Conducting a normality test to confirm that the data is normally distributed is necessary before moving forward with the paired

sample t-test analysis of the study hypothesis. For the normalcy test in this investigation, the Shapiro-Wilk test was utilised. For both pre- and post-test data, Table 3 displays the results of the Shapiro-Wilk test. The pre-test has a significance of 0.595 and the post-test has a significance of 0.948 according to the Shapiro-Wilk results. An analysis of the data's overall distribution to determine whether it deviates from a similar normal distribution is done using the Shapiro-Wilk test. If there is no significant difference between the sample distribution and the normal distribution ($p > 0.005$), the test is considered non-significant. Indicating that the data are normal, the Shapiro-Wilk test value is higher than 0.05. Consequently, it is decided to reject the null hypothesis. This leads to a normally distribution of the pre-test and post-test data in this investigation. The study hypothesis was examined using a paired sample t-test after the data's normal distribution was confirmed. To investigate H0 and H1, two hypotheses, the paired sample t-test method was employed. As stated at the outset of the investigation, the null hypothesis (H0) states that there is no significant change in student performance between before and after utilising the Interactive AR Textbook. The research hypothesis is to determine whether or not this study will accept or reject H0. In this investigation, 0.05 is the confidence threshold. The hypothesis H0 is rejected if the obtained confidence level is greater than 0.05.

Table 3. Shapiro-Wilk Test

Shapiro-Wilk	Statistic	df	Sig.
Pre-Test Score	0.975	314	0.595
Post-Test Score	0.986	314	0.948

Table 4. Mean and standard deviation

	N	Min	Standard Deviation
Pre-Test	314	57.94	14.721
Post-Test	314	78.13	12.447

The pre-test mean is 57.94, and the post-test mean is 78.13, according to paired sample statistics, as indicated in Table 4. Table 5 displays the significant value less than 0.05 for the paired sample t-test result, which is $t = 14.721$, $p = 0.000$. Consequently, it is decided to reject the null hypothesis. Results demonstrate how using The Interactive AR Textbook greatly raised student performance. Student proficiency with the alphabet is enhanced via interactive AR textbooks. As stated by Düzyol et al., mobile applications can support Grade 1 students' elementary school 3M learning. This study supports their findings (DÜZYOL, YILDIRIM, and ÖZYILMAZ 2022). Furthermore, mobile applications can aid in raising student performance (Özeren and Top 2023) Bonilla et al., have highlighted several benefits of utilising mobile applications for education, including cost and time savings, increased accessibility, and increased interest, consistent with the findings of the study (Bonilla-Sánchez et al. 2022).

Table 5. Paired Sample Test

	Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. 2- tail	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the				
				Lower				Upper
Pre-Test Score								
Post-Test Score	12.771	5.694	0.962	10.816	14.727	13.271	302	0.000

3.2 Motivation of Grade 1 Student

A total of seven questionnaire items were examined by knowledgeable teachers on student motivation while using the programme, and practically all of them received excellent comments. There is a clear indication that students take pleasure in the difficulty of studying this content. Because they have a passion for learning, they are always acquiring new information and learning more than what is needed of them. Additionally, it appears that the students are quite pleased with the progress they have made in recognising and pronouncing the vowel a, e, i, o, and u, which motivates them to continue their education as illustrated in Figure 15. Students are also noticed to be interested in reading more extensively about certain pages from the Malay language textbook that serves as the application. This is something that can be observed. As the learning process progresses, they experience a surge of bodily excitement.

The Interactive AR Textbook has a substantial impact on student performance, as indicated by the findings. Consistent with the results of prior, this discovery demonstrates that technology possesses the capacity to enhance academic performance and inspire students to acquire new knowledge, consistent with the findings of the study (Fiusa, Peres, and Marques 2023; Jdaitawi et al. 2023; Yusof and Jalil 2021). Further, students demonstrated considerable enthusiasm for mobile application-based ABC alphabet learning sessions. Learning activities are designed to encourage independent exploration and discovery, which is a preference of preschoolers. The disparity in scores between the pre-test and the post-test indicates that the use of the mobile application resulted in a higher score discrepancy than the initial score. This study provides support for this view, concerning the use of technology in the classroom, the study's findings are also consistent with those of Kwok et al., Özeren et al., a widely acknowledged viewpoint that technology enhances students' motivation and engagement with Malay textbooks (KSSR) and facilitates their learning (Kwok, Kwong, and Wong 2022; Özeren and Top 2023).

Figure 15. Grade 1 Primary School students in Perak are overjoyed with the Interactive AR Textbook

4. DISCUSSION

Several limitations apply to this investigation. Initially, the content is limited to the subtopic of vowel comprehension, specifically a, e, i, o, and u. Further research could be conducted to explore the evolution of mobile applications designed for students, with the inclusion of supplementary subjects like the reading of longer essays, which would serve to enhance the practical skills of young children. A second limitation of this investigation is the small sample size from Perak State. Respondents for future studies may be selected from a variety of groups. Primary school students from levels 1 and 2 may participate in the survey. By expanding the study's scope or incorporating additional groups, the conclusions will have a more comprehensive and high-quality nature. Functionally, the mobile application utilised in this research has its own set of limitations. Due to this circumstance, mobile applications are incomplete and have restricted functionality. Consequently, further functionalities may be integrated into this mobile application in subsequent iterations.

5. CONCLUSION

Grade 1 students who are enrolled in primary schools benefit from The Interactive AR Textbook in terms of both their comprehension and their motivation to acquire vowel a, e, i, o, and u. Additionally, the findings of this study demonstrate that a mobile application that is based on augmented reality has the potential to be utilised as one of the most effective learning aids in order to enhance the comprehension of grade 1 students about two-dimensional or three-dimensional design and animation. When it comes to teaching vowels a, e, i, o, and u, this study came to the conclusion that the combination of teaching delivery and facilitation methods with the utilisation of mobile applications is more effective than the traditional teaching methods. Through the implementation of the Interactive AR Textbook approach, a total of 314 grade 1 student attending a primary school in the state of Perak shown significant improvement in their academic performance. Despite the fact that they are updated with the most recent technology, Bahasa Melayu textbooks continue to serve as the primary reference for learning. Because of this, other researchers in the future can use this study as a guide and reference to help them with their own research.

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